

ON THE STOKES-BRINKMAN COUPLING WITH ANISOTROPIC NAVIER SLIP AND EFFECTIVE VISCOSITY FOR FLOW SIMULATIONS IN DUAL-SCALE FIBROUS POROUS MEDIA

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ABSTRACT

In this work, the Stokes-Brinkman model has been applied to investigate a flow in a channel coupling with a flow in a fibrous porous medium. According to our previous work [J. Lu et al., Composites part A, vol. 100, p. 9-19], the anisotropic slip coefficient at the interface between the channel flow and the fibrous porous medium has been characterized using the flow rate matching method. The effective viscosity in the Brinkman equation, which should also be anisotropic, was found to be as a function of the slip coefficient. By accurately characterizing the permeability and the effective viscosity, the Brinkman model with a pure domain can be applied to replace the actual fibrous porous medium, with which the computing cost will be expected to reduce considerably. An example problem has been solved numerically to validate the accuracy of the Brinkman model with such a series of non-identity effective viscosity ratios, it was found that, the averaged velocity at the interface from the actual flow agrees extremely well with the velocity at the interface using the Stokes-Brinkman model, so as to the Darcy velocity far away from the interface.

1 INTRODUCTION

When there is a flow over the porous medium, the velocity at the fluid/porous interface has been proved to be several orders of magnitude greater than the Darcy velocity u_D , which implies the existence of the thin boundary layer adjacent to the interface. Beavers and Joseph [1] proposed a mathematic assumption to force the velocity at the interface scaling with the velocity gradient (e.g. $u - u_D = \beta \partial u / \partial n$, with β being slip coefficient), which has been validated by their own experimental results. On the other hand, in order to account for the transitional flow between boundaries, Brinkman [2] extended the traditional form of Darcy's law by adding the Brinkman term (e.g. $\mu d^2 u / dy^2 - \mu / K u = dp / dx$, with μ being effective viscosity). It is believed that Brinkman's extension of Darcy's law is mathematically and physically preferable to Darcy's law when examining the boundary layer effects adjacent to the interface in porous medium [3,4]. Neale [5] analytically solved a channel flow coupled with a flow through the porous media. Comparison between the theoretical solution at the interface and Beavers and Joseph's assumption showed that the effective viscosity ratio is identical to squares of the slip coefficient by Beavers and Joseph (e.g. $\mu / \mu = \alpha_{BJ}^2$). Even though the effective viscosity ratio is customarily regarded as identity, in our previous work [6], using the flow rate matching method, we have provided the value of the slip coefficient α_{BJ} as a function of fibre volume fraction in the fibrous porous media.

2 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

According to our previous work on characterizing the anisotropic slip coefficient for the flow over the fibrous porous media, the expression of the slip coefficient can be expressed as:

$$\beta_\theta = \frac{4 - Q_\theta^*}{(Q_\theta^* - 1)H - 6K_\theta / H} \quad (\theta = \parallel \text{ or } \perp), \quad (1)$$

with Q_{θ}^* being the flow rate ratio, “||” denotes longitudinal direction and “ \perp ” is transverse direction. Combining Eq. (7) and (8) and the relation that $\beta = \alpha/\sqrt{K}$, one can readily get the value of the effective viscosity in the Brinkman equation. Plotted in Figure 2 is the effective viscosity ratio μ/μ_0 as a function of the fiber volume fractions for different packing structures in both longitudinal and transverse directions. It is shown that the effective viscosity ratios decrease as the fiber volume fraction increases for all the three different packing structures in both longitudinal and transverse directions. For various packing structures, the effective viscosity in the transverse direction is larger than the one in the longitudinal direction when the fibers are sparsely packed, and the opposite results appear in the densely packed region.

Figure 1: The effective viscosity ratio μ/μ_0 as a function of the fiber volume fractions for different packing structures and in both longitudinal and transverse directions

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